

Varietal resistance to whitebacked planthopper

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Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) regularly damages rice in Uttar Pradesh. The standard evaluation system was used to screen 531 rice varieties for WBPH resistance in the greenhouse. Thirty-six varieties were resistant (see table). Screening data showed that N22 with *Wbph 1* gene for resistance to WBPH was not resistant. However, breeding lines IR13458-7-2-1-1-3-3 and IR17307-11-2-3-2 from N22 crosses showed resistant reaction. IR15797-74-1-3-2, derived from an IR2035-117-3 cross, was also resistant. The susceptibility

of N22 at Pantnagar may indicate the presence of an inhibitory gene. Further investigation is needed. □

Whitebacked planthopper-resistant rice varieties, Pantnagar, India.

Variety	Average damage ^a	Resistance ^b
ARC5780	5.0	MR
ARC5838	4.6	MR
ARC6564	5.0	MR
ARC6579	4.2	MR
ARC6624	4.2	MR
ARC10464	4.6	MR
ARC11128	3.8	MR
ARC11220	3.9	MR
ARC11321	5.0	MR
ARC11324	3.0	R
Babawee	2.3	R
Balmawee	1.0	R
IET6288	2.2	R
IR2415-90-4-3	3.0	R
IR13384-79-2	4.7	MR
IR13458-7-2-1-1-3-3	3.0	R
IR13458-50-2-3-3-2	4.6	MR

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Variety	Average damage ^a	Resistance ^b
IR15529-175-2-3-2	3.8	MR
IR15795-199-3-3	5.0	MR
IR15797-74-1-3-2	2.1	R
IR17307-11-2-3-2	1.5	R
IR17494-32-2-4	4.8	MR
IR17496-2-25-1	2.6	R
IR1 339	3.0	R
KAU1717	3.0	R
KAU25100	1.7	R
M22-33-3-1	4.5	MR
Ptb 19	0.5	R
Ptb 21	2.1	R
P'tb 33	2.7	R
Rathu Heenati	1.0	R
RAU4000-105	3.2	MR
RNR1576	4.0	MR
RP1045-714-3-3	4.7	MR
Sinna Sivappu	2.0	R
Suduru Samba	1.7	R

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

Rice resistance to yellow stem borer

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Rice varieties are being screened for resistance to yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India. This species is a serious pest in double-cropped areas and causes deadhearts and whiteheads at crop vegetative and reproductive stages.

Field-collected moths were put in cages with potted rice plants to oviposit.

Emerging first-instar larvae were used to test varieties for resistance. Because varietal susceptibility varies with age, screening was done at seedling, tillering,

and reproductive stages.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm seedling screening trays filled with soil. Twenty days after sowing one freshly emerged larva/seedling was released. Trays were covered with a glass cage for 2 days to prevent the dispersal of the larvae, and to avoid predators.

Twenty-five days after germination 1 seedling/10-cm pot was planted. When the plants were 40 days old, one freshly hatched larva/tiller was placed on the top-most auricle. Plants were covered with polyester cages and tests were replicated three times. Jaya was the susceptible check. Deadhearts were counted 7 and 10 days after release at seedling and vegeta-

tive stages.

At reproductive stage, 70 days after sowing, one larva was released/tiller and plants were covered with a cylindrical polyester cage. Ten days after release whiteheads were counted. Percent deadhearts and whiteheads was calculated by:

$$\frac{\% \text{ deadhearts (whiteheads) in entry}}{\% \text{ deadhearts (whiteheads) in susceptible check}} \times 100$$

Among the 170 varieties tested, W1263 and IR136-41-4 were moderately resistant at the seedling stage, and resistant at vegetative and reproductive stages. CO18, IR136-39-39, and Sornavazhai were moderately resistant at all stages. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Other pests

Rodent damage on some rice varieties at Aduthurai, India

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The Indian mole rat *Bunadicota bengulensis* (Gray) and the grass rat *Millur-*

Rodent damage to some rice varieties at Tamil Nadu, India^a

Variety	Damage (%)	Variety	Damage (%)	Variety	Damage (%)
IET5 74 2	0.0	Ponni	0.6	Co 38	1.5
TNAU15868	0.2	CR1009	0.7	NLR9672	1.5
Co 40	0.4	Co 25	0.9	White Ponni	2.2
IET5046	0.5	IET5852	1.4	AD3488	2.6

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